

Digital Library Access in a Telepathology Network: Application in Gynecological Cancer

F. Schnorrenberg¹, V. Tanos², C.S. Pattichis¹, F. Iacovou³, K. Kyriacou⁴, C.N. Schizas¹

¹*Department of Computer Science, University of Cyprus, Kallipoleos 75, P.O. Box 537, CY-1678 Nicosia, Cyprus, e-mail {csfranks, pattichi, schizas}@cs.ucy.ac.cy*

³*Department of Histology, Nicosia General Hospital, Nicosia, Cyprus*

²*Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Hadassah University Hospital, Ein-Kerem, P.O. Box 12000, Jerusalem 91120, Israel*

⁴*Department of Electron Microscopy, The Cyprus Institute for Neurology and Genetics, P.O. Box 3462, Nicosia, Cyprus, e-mail Kyriacos@mdrtc.cing.ac.cy*

Abstract: Histopathologists may utilize a telepathology network to access a digital library or to consult a specialist using available video and clinical data, if the necessary expertise is not locally available, a second opinion is needed, or a comparison with past similar data is indicated. Moreover, a telepathology network and in particular a digital library can be used interactively by medical experts to aid preparatory research, follow-up research, archiving, training, and standardization. The main objective of this paper is to demonstrate the feasibility and need for specialized image content-based retrieval methods to a digital library for gynecological cancer within a telepathology network. The implemented context-based retrieval method presented in this paper is based on the Biopsy Analysis Support System (BASS). This system uses breast cancer biopsy images to demonstrate the functionality of content-based image retrieval methods.

1. Introduction

Gynecological cancer (breast, ovarian, endometrial, cervical) consists of a large number of tumors with variable presentation and often unpredictable malignant potential, making patient management demanding but also challenging. In addition, the necessity to preserve the patient's sexuality and fertility potential and the requirement to offer optimum treatment to combat malignancies complicate management decisions.

Surgery plays a significant role in the management of most gynecological benign and malignant tumors. Optimized first surgery may provide in this context a survival advantage. However, even the most experienced surgeon is totally reliant on intraoperative histopathological evaluation for distinguishing between malignant and benign disease. In practice, expert histopathologists with experience in each human body system cannot be found next to each surgeon. As a result in most cases, therapy is based on postoperative histopathological diagnosis including second opinions, such as consultations from experts at remote sites. Ideally, however, patient benefit should be optimized at first surgery through timely and accurate histopathological diagnosis. In general, a telepathology network will offer on-line dynamic intraoperative and postoperative consultations between a panel of experts via the transmission of video (laparoscopic scenes), still images (histopathologic specimen images), and clinical data. In this context a digital library can be used by medical experts to interactively examine past similar case studies for preparatory research, follow-up research, archiving, training, and standardization.

The main objective of this paper is to demonstrate the feasibility and need for specialized image content-based retrieval methods to a digital library for gynecological cancer within a telepathology network. The implemented context-based retrieval method presented in this paper is based on the Biopsy Analysis Support System (BASS) [5]. This system uses breast cancer biopsy images to demonstrate the functionality of content-based image retrieval methods.

Expected benefits of the telepathology network and the digital library will be focused on improving diagnostic standards. All participating histopathology laboratories will benefit from the standardization efforts regarding tissue processing which have to take place to enable specialized histopathologists from one site to assess images from specimens, processed at another site of the network. Additionally, the use of the network and library will lead to less radical operations, less hospitalizations, and less patient complications.

In the next section the telepathology network architecture is discussed. This is followed by the presentation of a content-based biopsy image retrieval interface based on the BASS system. Finally, results are presented in

section 4 and concluding remarks are given in section 5.

2. Telepathology Network Architecture and Assessment

A typical telepathology system involves surgery, histopathology, and telepathologic interaction between medical experts (Figure 1). Laparoscopic video sequences may be reviewed by the expert histopathologist who in turn may provide further advice to the surgeon. Depending on the diagnosis, additional specialized biopsy slides may be prepared and assessed.

In urgent cases intraoperative diagnoses will be attempted to help the surgeon optimize first surgery. If the necessary expertise is not locally available or a second opinion is needed, histopathologists may utilize the telepathology network to consult a specialist or to query a digital library using available video and clinical data.

Figure 1. Telepathology Network Architecture.

In the digital library the biopsy slide image data together with other clinical data and possibly pre-existing patient data will be stored and updated. In addition, patient related information (virtual patient record) and general information exchange within health care networks will be supported. Moreover, the digital library will contain information regarding for example laboratory tissue processing protocols and complete case studies including digital image data. Operational standards compliant with CEN TC251 guidelines in medical informatics regarding for example medical data interchange, and exchange of clinical laboratory information will be monitored and applied throughout the telepathology network.

For adequate access to such electronic repositories of data and knowledge, queries should ideally be based both on textual data, such as patient name, or a manually entered case description, and image data, such as biopsy slide image data. The need arises particularly in telepathology [2] to archive biopsy image data and access it later based on its contents or similarity to other image data. For preparatory research, follow-up research, training, archival, and standardization, the on-line digital library will be a valuable tool which can also be used during

interactive sessions to examine past similar cases.

3. Content-Based Access to Image Data in Digital Libraries

While content-based access to image and video databases is already a reality [1, 3, 10], recent research work shows that depending on the image data and the desired search mode some approaches are more adequate than others [4]. In particular, in the medical domain global properties of an image, while at times simple and efficient to compute [9], are often less important compared to structural and semantic descriptions of image content [3]. However, reasoning over structural and semantic details or objects in an image requires specialized functionality for each image domain. Examples where the local structure is important are magnetic resonance (MRI), x-ray imagery, and biopsy images. BASS [5], previously used for breast cancer biopsy slide image analysis [6], has been extended to include indexing and content-based retrieval of biopsy slide images from a database of cases. Thus, utilizing standard database queries for textual data and BASS for specialized content-based access to biopsy image data, the digital library can efficiently be accessed even from remote sites.

Figure 2. Diagram of the Biopsy Analysis Support System (BASS) [7]: a. Overview of the system, b. Biopsy analysis module.

3.1 Material

A database of cases (DBC) (Figure 2a, IV) was generated using eighteen breast cancer biopsy slides, immunolabelled for prognostic factors estrogen or progesterone (ERICA-kit, Abbot, UK) and counterstained with haematoxylin to contrast positively stained nuclei (brown color) with negative nuclei (blue color). A medical expert selected and digitized up to three regions of interest from each slide at x400 magnification (Zeiss Axiophot microscope, SONY DXC-980P camera) in 24 bit color and 640*480 pixel spatial resolution. Additional information for each case included a unique registration number (CASENO), which can be used to cross-reference a case in other databases external to BASS, and a diagnostic index which was manually assigned in the laboratory routine assessment (LABSCORE). In its current form, BASS features two main modules (Figure 2): biopsy analysis (Figure 2a, I; Figure 2b) and database access (Figure 2a, III).

3.2 Biopsy Analysis (Figure 2a, I; Figure 2b)

To date, breast cancer biopsy slides are compared by reviewing diagnostic indices, and usually through lengthy lightmicroscopic examination. Diagnostic indices describe the status of prognostic factors, such as estrogen and progesterone, as visualized in breast cancer nuclei populations. The diagnostic index is computed by classifying nuclei according to staining intensity and then estimating the proportions of nuclei with different staining intensities in the biopsy slide. Commercial computer-aided systems compute their own diagnostic index as a function of total nuclei area and the optical density (see [5] for references).

BASS' biopsy analysis module is divided into a standardization stage (Figure 2b, I.1), an adaptive nuclei detection stage (Figure 2b, I.2), and a trainable neural network based classification stage (Figure 2b, I.3). The

output of the analysis module (Figure 2a, II) describes the content of each biopsy image.

The standardization stage (Figure 2b, I.1) yields an image that has been corrected to account for illumination differences across the optical field due to the light microscope. The digitized biopsy image is pixelwise and channelwise divided by a background image that in turn was obtained using a blank biopsy slide. All digitized images are transformed from RGB color space to the YUV color space. In YUV space the luminance (Y channel) and the chromaticity (U, V channel) of a color images are clearly separated. BASS uses the luminance image for the detection of candidate nuclei, while for the classification module utilizes features based on all three channels.

BASS automatically detects individual breast cancer nuclei candidates using receptive fields [5] (Figure 2b, I.2). The input to the detection stage consists of the luminance channel of the original color image. The image is repeatedly convoluted and the individual intensity values are remapped (squashed) using an on-center-off surround type receptive field filter and a logistic squashing function. After less than five iterations the histogram of the image develops a characteristic bimodal shape, which is used to determine a threshold to obtain a binary image. The centers of the remaining disconnected image structures are determined using morphological operations. These centers are interpreted as the candidate nuclei center locations. At this point the detection process is complete.

BASS' classification stage (Figure 2b, I.3) uses a widely accepted manual grading scheme for accurately assessing staining intensity and heterogeneity of the nuclei populations in the biopsy slides [8]. According to the grading scheme nuclei are assigned to one of five staining intensity classes (negative, weak, moderate, strong, very strong). Depending on the proportions of the classified nuclei, one final diagnostic index out of five possible values (0, 1+, 2+, 3+, 4+) is assigned to the biopsy. The input to the classification stage consists of six-dimensional feature vectors. The feature vectors are based on a fixed number of pixels in a small circular neighborhood of each nuclei candidate center location. The features are optical density, two chromaticity values, a variance based texture measure, and the average optical density and variance of all nuclei candidates in the biopsy image. A neural network which obtained 72 % correct classification on a test set is the centerpiece of BASS' classification stage.

3.3 Database Access (Figure 2a, III)

All features used for comparing two biopsy slides are precomputed using BASS in either an interactive or automated fashion. Thus, the actual comparison of cases can be performed without reading any of the images except for display purposes. After the computed features and classification results have been stored in the database of cases, queries can be formulated (Table 1).

The scope of queries that a database of breast biopsy slides has to address is of a *perceptual* and *task-specific* nature. The queries take the form of textual compound expressions as illustrated in Table 1. The expressions contain feature value lists and 'don't care' values, based on the above mentioned assessment scheme which classifies nuclei into 5 classes and distinguishes 5 different diagnostic indices. To find matching cases, one can specify (see Table 1a) the unique case number (CASENO), the type of stain (TYPE), the name (NAME), the diagnostic index manually obtained in the laboratory routine (LABSCORE), the diagnostic index assigned using BASS (SYSSCORE), occurrence of nuclei classes (NUCCLASS), and a heterogeneity coefficient (HETERO), which is based on a normalized variance measure of all members of the nuclei classes in each image. Similar images can be retrieved by using the construct specified in Table 1b. A range of biopsy images can be specified to find other images which match given maximal deviation from the diagnostic index (SCORE_DEV), heterogeneity coefficient (HETERO), and occurrence of nuclei classes (NUCCLASS).

Table 1. Content-based query (adapted from [7]).

a. Find <i>matching</i> cases	b. Find <i>similar</i> cases
<pre> SELECT(FROM= dbc, MATCH(CASENO= ['1678-92', ...], TYPE= ['ER', ...], NAME= ['substring', ...], LABSCORE= [-1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1], SYSSCORE= [-1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1], NUCCLASS= [0/1, 0/1, 0/1, 0/1, 0/1] </pre>	<pre> SELECT(FROM=dbc, LIKE= dbc(<IDX>), USING(SCORE_DEV= 0/1/2/3 HETERO= ['LT', 'GT', 'EQ'] NUCCLASS= [-1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1]) </pre>

HETERO= ['LT num.', 'GT num.', 'EQ num.'])	
'-1' indicates 'no', '0' stands for 'don't care', and '1' symbolizes 'yes'.	

4. Results

Once a biopsy slide has been analyzed with BASS, the results are stored in an image independent datastructure. This datastructure can easily be accessed to retrieve and compare any features relevant for a content-based query.

Sample queries supported by the system are given in Figure 3a,b and their results are illustrated in Figure 3c-f. The query in Figure 3a demonstrates a search for matching cases, i.e. images, of staining type 'ER' (estrogen) to which BASS has assigned a diagnostic index of 4+ (SYSSCORE) and a heterogeneity coefficient greater than 0.75. The response of the system is illustrated in Figure 3c,d. In Figure 3b, a sample query is shown, whose goal it is to find similar cases, i.e. images. In particular, the query will flag cases that contain negative nuclei, weakly stained nuclei, but not strongly stained, nor very strongly stained nuclei (NUCCLASS), and which may differ up to 1 point in the diagnostic index (SCORE_DEV). The response of the system is given in Figure 3e,f.

<p>a. Find <i>matching</i> cases (images (c), (d) below)</p> <pre> SELECT_MATCHING{ FROM= database, USING(CASENO= ['1678-92', ...], TYPE= ['Estrogen', ...], NAME= ['substring', ...], LAB_SCORE= [-1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1], SYS_SCORE= [-1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1, -1/0/1], NUCCLASS= [0/1, 0/1, 0/1, 0/1, 0/1] HETERO= ['< x', '> x', '= x']) </pre>	<p>b. Find <i>similar</i> cases (images (e), (f) below)</p> <pre> SELECT_SIMILAR{ FROM= database, LIKE= database([<IDX>]), USING(SCORE_DEV= 0/1/2/3 HETERO= ['< x', '> z', '= x'] NUCCLASS= [-1/0/1,-1/0/1,-1/0/1,-1/0/1,-1/0/1]) </pre>
<p>0 ≤ x ≤ 1; '-1' indicates 'no', '0' stands for 'don't care', and '1' symbolizes 'yes'.</p>	
<p>c.</p>	
<p>TYPE: ER, HETERO: 0.79, SYSSCORE: 4+, 346 nuclei detected: 9 negative, 9 weak, 163 moderate, 151 strong, 14 very strong</p>	<p>TYPE: ER, HETERO: 0.82, SYSSCORE: 4+, 382 nuclei detected: 0 negative, 169 weak, 34 moderate, 179 strong, 0 very strong</p>
<p>e.</p>	
<p>TYPE: ER, SYSSCORE: 2+, 156 nuclei detected: 54 negative, 93 weak, 9 moderate, 0 strong, 0 very strong</p>	<p>TYPE: ER, SYSSCORE: 1+, 237 nuclei detected: 24 negative, 213 weak, 0 moderate, 0 strong, 0 very strong</p>

Figure 3. Results of database queries (adapted from [7]): The original images are color images and larger in size. Gradations in nuclei staining intensity, which are important for classification of nuclei, cannot satisfactorily be resolved in grayscale. Thus, only coarse differences among nuclei populations are visible.

5. Concluding Remarks

BASS provides a general interface for retrieval and characterization of biopsy slides. Visual similarity of cases can be specified in terms of a diagnostic index, maximal deviation from diagnostic index, heterogeneity of nuclei staining intensity, and occurrence of particular nuclei classes. While it was demonstrated that BASS can support content-based queries, further research is needed to explore the full potential of the approach in a realistic setting.

Telemedicine and in particular telepathology have the potential to improve health care standards by delivering cost effective medical expertise and knowledge within and across regional boundaries. In particular, existing, geographically localized, pathology centers with specialized medical expertise can provide their services via a telepathology network to general medical centers ensuring maximum patient benefit in the case of gynecological cancer. Once established this network will also be exploited in other areas of telepathology which present diagnostic difficulties.

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